

three planes, (312), (213) and (321). Each sample was thoroughly mixed with 25% NaCl which served as a standard, so that the observed values of $\sin \theta$ for the solid solution lines could be corrected directly for absorption and instrumental errors. The lattice constant of NaCl at 26° was taken to be 5.64034 Å¹⁶. A least squares calculation on the corrected values of $\sin \theta$ for the three reflections then gave the two parameters, a_0 and c_0 , for each sample. The average probable error in unit cell parameters is less than ± 0.05 Å.

Results and Discussion

The observed value of molar g-atom ratio of $\frac{\text{Ca}}{\text{P}}, \frac{\text{Sr}}{\text{P}}, \frac{\text{Ba}}{\text{P}}$ for the end members and $\frac{\text{Ca} + \text{Sr} + \text{Ba}}{\text{P}}$ were found to be equal to 1.664 (theoretical 1.67) and is consistent with the formation of homogeneous solid solution¹³. This was further supported by the closeness of the values of molar volumes of the end members and those of the intermediate samples which lie within the range of end members.

The formation of solid solutions can be further confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis. Apatites crystallize in a hexagonal structure with space group $P6_3/m^{17,18}$. Lattice parameters showed increase of c/a ratio consequent upon the introduction of bigger ions, $[\text{Sr}^{2+} (1.13 \text{ \AA}) \text{ and } \text{Ba}^{2+} (1.35 \text{ \AA})]$, in place of $\text{Ca}^{2+} (0.99 \text{ \AA})$ in the apatite lattice. Such dilation with the proportion of Ca-Sr-BaHA was evident as the unit cell volume of the samples calculated on the basis of the experimentally determined lattice constant increased with the proportion of strontium and barium in Ca-Sr-BaHA.

References

1. W. F. NEUMAN and M. W. NEUMAN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, 53, 1.
2. R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Bone and Joint Surg.*, 1952, 34, 389.
3. R. WALLACYS and T. CHAUDRON, *Compt. rend.*, 1950, 231, 355.
4. E. HAYEK and STADLMANN, *Angew. Chem.*, 1955, 67, 327.
5. A. F. WELLS, "Structural Inorganic Chemistry", Oxford University Press, London, 1950, p. 70.
6. J. R. VAN WAZER, "Phosphorous and Its Compounds", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, Vol. 1, p. 590.
7. J. R. VAN WAZER, "Phosphorous and Its Compounds", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1966, Vol. 2, p. 144.
8. PREMA N. PATEL, *J. Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1978, 20, 804.
9. PREMA N. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 4, 410.
10. PREMA N. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1980, 42, 1129.
11. E. E. BERRY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29, 1585.
12. PREMA N. PATEL, *Z. anal. Chem.*, communicated.
13. J. R. PARTINGTON, "An Advanced Treatise on Physical Chemistry", Longman Green and Co., Vol. 3, p. 121.
14. L. V. AZAROFF, "Elements of X-ray Crystallography", McGraw Hill Book Co., London, 1968, Chapter II.
15. OULLITY, "Elements of X-ray Diffraction", pp. 309-318.
16. M. STRAUMANIS and A. LEVINS, *Z. Phys.*, 1938, 109, 728.
17. M. MEHMEL, *Z. Krist.*, 1930, 75, 323; ST. NARRAY-SZABO, *Z. Krist.*, 1930, 75, 387.
18. H. HENTSCHEL, "Zentf. Mineral Geol.", 1923, p. 609 for a and e X-ray study.

Synthesis and Structural Studies of β -Mercapto Ethyl(2-Hydroxy-5-Methyl Phenyl)-Benzalimine and β -Mercapto Ethyl Anil of 1-(2',4'-Dihydroxy Phenyl)Pentane Complexes of Pd(II)

V. K. RASTOGI*, A. K. KATIYAR†, R. C. SAXENA†
and
A. K. KOTNALA†

Molecular Spectroscopy Research Laboratory,
Department of Physics, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001

Manuscript received 22 May 1981, revised 5 December 1981,
accepted 7 January 1982

IN view of the reported anticancer activity of platinum metals we describe the preparation and characterisation of some complexes of Pd(II) with the Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-5-methyl benzophenone, 2,4-dihydroxy valerophenone and β -mercapto ethylamine hydrochloride. The compounds have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic measurements, ir and electronic spectral data and a square planar structure has been assigned to them.

Experimental

$[Pd(C_{10}H_{15}NSO)_2H_2O]$: Palladium Schiff base complex was synthesized by adding a calculated amount (2.134 g; 10 m mole) of palladium chloride to an ethanolic solution of β -mercapto ethyl(2-hydroxy-5-methyl phenyl)benzalimine (3.07 g; 10 m mole) in equimolar ratio 1 : 1 (M : L). The orange coloured precipitate thus formed was filtered, washed with ethanol and finally with ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

$[Pd(C_{13}H_{17}NSO_2)H_2O].3H_2O$: An equimolar mixture of palladium chloride (2.134 g; 10 m mole) and β -mercapto ethyl anil of 1-(2',4'-dihydroxy phenyl)pentane (2.895 g; 10 m mole) in ethanol was refluxed on a water bath for ~2 hr. An orange coloured complex was obtained which was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are orange in colour and insoluble in water. Analytical data of the complexes suggest 1 : 1 (M : L) stoichiometry. Magnetic measurements indicate that both the complexes are diamagnetic at room temperature, suggesting a D_{4h} symmetry around the central metal ion as expected for a d^8 configuration.

The electronic spectra of both the complexes show three bands in the regions 16000-20000, 23500-29000 and 29000-33000 cm^{-1} which are assigned to the

* On leave from Lajpat Rai College, Sahibabad-201 005.

† Department of Chemistry, M. M. College, Modinagar-201 204.

${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ transitions, respectively in the order of increasing energy³. The bands occurring beyond 34000 cm^{-1} have been assigned as charge transfer bands to the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2u}$ transition³. The band occurring at ~ 30000 and 32000 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (C=S) and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (C=N) transitions⁴ of the ligands. The single electron parameters Δ_1 , Δ_2 and Δ_3 for these complexes come out to be 20920, 9172, 4637 and 22420, 11532, 3717, respectively.

The strong bands occurring at 3680 cm^{-1} in their spectra of $C_{16}H_{15}NSO$ and at 3650 cm^{-1} in their spectra of $C_{16}H_{17}NSO_2$ may be assigned to OH stretching vibrations. These bands seem to disappear in the spectra of the chelates forming (M-O) bond. The phenolic (C-O) stretching vibration in the ligands occurs as strong band in the region $1200\text{--}1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$. On chelation, this band is shifted to higher frequency. The bands resulting from the ligands $C_{16}H_{15}NSO$ and $C_{16}H_{17}NSO_2$ at 1590 and 1620 cm^{-1} correspond to $\nu(C=N)$ vibrations⁵. A sharp negative shift in $\nu(C=N)$ to 1530 and 1600 cm^{-1} , respectively in the complexes of the two ligands indicates the involvement of the nitrogen atom in bond formation with Pd(II) atom. The disappearance of the stretching frequency of -SH observed in the free ligands at 2560 and 2570 cm^{-1} , clearly indicates the loss of thionic proton on coordination and formation of a new bond between metal and sulphur. Both the complexes showed a broad band in the region $3400\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating the presence of a water molecule. It is thus inferred that the ligands acting as tridentate occupy three positions on Pd^{2+} ion while the fourth is occupied by a water molecule.

References

1. J. S. DWIVEDI and U. AGARWAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 657.
2. V. B. RANA, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut University, Meerut, 1975.
3. W. RUDZINSKI, G. T. BEHNKE and Q. FERNADO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 1206.
4. I. HANAZAKI and S. NAGAKURA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 648.
5. K. NAKANISHI, "Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy", Holden Day, Inc., San Francisco, 1962, p. 50.

Alkali Metal Complexes : Adducts of Alkali Metal Salts of Some Organic Acids with 1,10-Phenanthroline

DHARM PRAKASH

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005
and

SHANKAR PRASAD SINGH

Department of Chemistry, A. N. College, Patna-800 013

Manuscript received 28 December 1981, revised 23 November 1982,
accepted 19 March 1983

THE interaction of alkali metal salts of organic acids with 1,10-phenanthroline has been investigated¹⁻³. We describe here the synthesis and

characterisation of a number of solid adducts of alkali metal salts of acetylacetonone, salicylaldehyde and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with the title ligand. They have the general formula ML_nL (M=Li, Na or K; L=deprotonated acetylacetonone, salicylaldehyde or *o*-hydroxyacetophenone; $n=1$ and $L'=1,10$ -phenanthroline). Elemental analyses, thermal, ir spectral and the solution studies of these solid adducts reveal that they are genuine complexes.

Experimental

Our usual method of synthesising these adducts was to take a suspension of an alkali metal salt in benzene in a test-tube and then to add 1,10-phenanthroline to it in 1:3 mole ratio. On stirring the mixture slowly, all the solids went into solution. The contents were then warmed for 5 min on a steam bath and cooled, when crystals of the adducts came apart. These were filtered, washed with cold benzene and dried in an electric oven at 80° .

Results and Discussion

The adducts of alkali metal salts of acetylacetonone, salicylaldehyde and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with 1,10-phenanthroline are white, bright yellow and light yellow, respectively.

Almost all the compounds are stable when stored under dry conditions. The transition/decomposition temperatures of all these adducts (except those of alkali metal salts of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone) are much higher than the melting point of the ligand. This seems to indicate that 1,10-phenanthroline in the adducts is essentially not present as free base or even as its hydrate, which melts at 117° and $93\text{--}94^\circ$, respectively and that the compounds are held together by forces stronger than the van der Waals forces.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared measurements of all the compounds were carried out in the region $4000\text{--}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in Nujol mulls.

The pertinent bands in the ir spectrum of 1,10-phenanthroline are 1505 , 854 and 738 cm^{-1} . The 1505 cm^{-1} band is the most intense band in the $1650\text{--}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region and is attributed to $\nu CC + \nu CN$ vibrations⁴. On complexation, this band shifts to a higher frequency by $5\text{--}10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and also exhibits a weak satellite on its low frequency side. The bands in the region $900\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are identified with motions of the ring hydrogen atoms moving in phase out-of-the-plane of the ring. The frequency at which absorption occurs will depend upon the number of adjacent hydrogen atoms around the ring. Since phenanthroline has three rings two of which are equivalent with three hydrogen atoms, and one with two adjacent hydrogen atoms, only two bands are observed, one at 738 cm^{-1} (assigned to out-of-plane motion of the H-atoms on the heterocyclic rings) and the other at 854 cm^{-1} (assigned to out-of-plane motion of hydrogen atoms on the